

Nanoscale surface and bulk electronic properties of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene unraveled by multimodal X-ray spectromicroscopy

Faidra Amargianou^{1,2}, *Peer Bärman*¹, *Hui Shao*³, *Pierre-Louis Taberna*³, *Patrice Simon*³, *Jesus Gonzalez-Julian*⁴, *Markus Weigand*¹, and *Tristan Petit*^{1,*}

¹ Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie GmbH, Albert-Einstein-Straße 15, 12489 Berlin, Germany

² Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, TU-Berlin, Hardenbergstr. 36, D-10623 Berlin, Germany

³ Université Paul Sabatier, CIRIMAT UMR CNRS 5085, 118 route de Narbonne, 31062 Toulouse, France

⁴ Institute of Mineral Engineering (GHI), Chair of Ceramics, RWTH Aachen, D-52074 Aachen, Germany

*E-mail: tristan.petit@helmholtz-berlin.de

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Two-dimensional layered materials, such as transition metal carbides or nitrides, known as MXenes, offer an ideal platform to investigate charge transfer processes in confined environment, relevant for energy conversion and storage applications. Their rich surface chemistry plays an essential role in the pseudocapacitive behavior of MXenes. However, the local distribution of surface functional groups over single flakes and within few- or multilayered flakes remains unclear. In this work, we introduce scanning X-ray microscopy (SXM) with simultaneous transmission and electron yield detection, enabling multimodal nanoscale chemical imaging with bulk and surface sensitivity, respectively, of individual MXene flakes. The Ti chemical bonding environment is found to significantly vary between few-layered HF-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes and multilayered molten salt (MS)-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes. *Post-mortem* analysis of MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ electrodes cycled in a Li-ion battery further illustrates that simultaneous bulk and surface chemical imaging using SXM offers a powerful method for characterizing the electrode-electrolyte interactions at the nanoscale.

1. Introduction

Van der Waals interactions in two-dimensional (2D) layered materials play a pivotal role in the physical properties of the individual 2D sheets. The top most layer may have other properties than buried layers, which are strongly influenced by Van der Waals forces depending on interlayer distances^[1-3]. The introduction of guest species through intercalation offers a means to fine-tune the chemical and electronic interactions between these layers^[4-5], which can have profound implications for electrochemical energy storage applications^[6-7]. The surface layer may exhibit unique electronic and chemical properties in contrast to the buried layers for layered materials due to the loss of these interactions with other layers. A comprehensive study for multilayered materials remains however elusive due to a scarcity of probing techniques offering both bulk and surface sensitivity down to single layers.

2D layered transition metal carbide, carbonitrides and nitrides, known as MXenes have a versatile chemistry that allows the tuning of properties for applications including energy storage^[8], optoelectronics^[9-10], electromagnetic interference shielding^[11], water purification^[12] and gas sensors^[13]. The general stoichiometry of MXenes correspond to $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, ($n= 1-4$), where M represents an early transition metal(s), X is either carbon and/or nitrogen, and T_x corresponds to the terminals (-F, OH-, O-, etc.) formed during the etching process. By now, a great number of MXene compositions were discovered, but $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene remains the most studied one, thanks to its easy synthesis, good stability and excellent electrochemical properties.

MXene has shown outstanding properties for electrochemical energy storage applications such as Li-ion battery^[14-15] and supercapacitors^[16]. Yet, fundamental questions persist about its pseudocapacitive energy storage mechanisms. Redox reactions on the surface of MXene particle, potentially influenced by Solid-Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) formation, might exhibit distinct characteristics compared to those within its interlayer spaces which are exposed to confined electrolytes and intercalated ions, emphasizing the need for thorough investigations of both surface and bulk chemical bonding^[17]. Most of the MXene currently applied in electrochemical energy storage devices are synthesized by a wet chemical etching of a MAX phase with hydrofluoric acid (HF)-containing solutions ($HF-Ti_3C_2T_x$)^[18], or Lewis acid etching using molten salts ($MS-Ti_3C_2T_x$)^[19]. On one hand, $Ti_3C_2T_x$ with F-rich terminating species are expected to be highly resilient to oxidation^[20]. On the other hand, $MS-Ti_3C_2T_x$ exhibited excellent electrochemical performance in Li-ion contained non-aqueous electrolyte compared to $HF-Ti_3C_2T_x$ ^[19].

Capturing the surface and bulk properties of monolayer, few-layered and multi-layered MXene remains experimentally very challenging on individual MXene flakes. While electron loss spectroscopy has enabled great understanding of the structure of single flakes MXenes, the energy resolution is usually too limited to capture the fine Ti chemical bonding^[21]. Scanning probe techniques such as tip-enhanced Raman spectroscopy allows high spatial resolution with high chemical sensitivity but is limited to the top layers^[22]. Additionally, MXenes, as other layered transition metal compounds, stand out due to the potent electronic correlations of the transition metal *d* orbitals and their high sensitivity to changes in the surrounding chemical environment^[23]. There is a therefore a strong need for a non-destructive technique that allows to probe both surface and bulk of MXene multilayered flakes with a large chemical sensitivity to the transition metal chemical bonding.

Soft X-rays absorption spectroscopy (XAS) allows the probing of fine electronic structure of the metal valence electrons and light elements present in the layered transition metal compounds.^[24-25] Specifically, for transition metal structures with termination groups found in MXenes, the crystal field interaction determines the shape, strength, and occupancy of electronic orbitals^[26]. X-ray PhotoElectron Emission Microscopy (XPEEM) has already been employed for investigating modification of the MXene surface chemistry upon cation intercalation in different individual $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ particles with nanometer spatial resolution^[27,28]. However, XPEEM is a surface sensitive technique due to the detection of photoemitted electrons only. While XPEEM have been performed on Li-ion battery electrodes, this approach are challenging due to the high porosity and roughness of such materials^[29].

Transmission imaging techniques with soft X-rays are ideal for monitoring changes in the local chemistry of few-layered materials, with guest-species between the interlayers or exposed to different environments. Full-field transmission X-ray microscopy (TXM) is capable of 2D imaging and tomography, as well as spectroscopic imaging. It has been employed as a useful tool to study morphology, chemical distributions, reaction dynamics, and degradation mechanisms in 2D layered and electrode materials^[30]. However, the rigid configuration of TXM is not appropriate for parallel collection of complementary information using a multimodal approach^[31]. Unlike TXM, Scanning Transmission X-ray Microscopy (STXM) allows, in addition to transmission detection, total fluorescence yield (TFY) and total electron yield (TEY) detections, which makes this technique ideal for a multimodal characterization of both surface and bulk chemistry.

In this work, we apply multimodal Scanning X-ray Microscopy (SXM) for simultaneous hyperspectral imaging of bulk and surface electronic properties of individual $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes. Single and few-layered HF-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes, and multilayered MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes are imaged by multimodal SXM. Transmission detection mode is used for bulk sensitivity, required to probe the surface chemistry in the MXene interlayer, while TEY mode allows high surface sensitivity for probing the top MXene layer. The results unravel the influence of different processing routes on Ti chemical bonding monitored by XAS at the Ti L- and O K-edge. Finally, multimodal SXM enables the chemical identification of the different components found in *post-mortem* analysis of MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes cycled in a Li-ion battery.

2. Methods

2.1. Simultaneous surface- and bulk-sensitive X-ray spectromicroscopy

In a conventional SXM setup, monochromatic X-rays are demagnified through a Fresnel Zone Plate (ZP), generating a finely focused microprobe. This microprobe scans across the specimen under examination in a raster pattern. An Order-Selecting Aperture (OSA) is placed between the ZP and the specimen to filter out all undesired diffraction orders, as shown in **Figure 1**. Multimodal SXM allows the detection of both transmitted X-rays (transmission mode) and drain current of released photoelectrons (TEY mode)^[32]. The bulk-sensitive transmission mode is acquired with an avalanche photodiode detector (APD) while the surface-sensitive TEY mode is recorded by amplifying the sample drain current. A bias voltage of +30 V is set between the sample holder and the OSA to remove parasitic electrons.

Figure 1. Scheme of a SXM setup. Monochromatic X-rays are focused through a FZP into a nanoprobe, which scans the specimen in a raster pattern. An OSA filters undesired diffraction orders. SXM images recorded on $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene in both transmission and TEY modes averaged at the Ti L-edge are shown.

Due to the short penetration depth of soft X-rays, thin samples are required for transmission detection,^[32] which may be challenging for the characterization of multilayered MXenes. While a single $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene layer is about 1 nm in thickness, multilayered MXene typically comprise stacked MXene layers of micrometric thickness that are too thick for transmission detection. Delaminated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, dispersed in water, on the other hand, primarily comprises single and few-layered MXene flakes with lateral dimensions of a few micrometers that can be used to form very thin films. With transmission measurements, saturation can occur when either the sample thickness or the absorption coefficient μ are too large^[33]. For the characterization of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene at the Ti L-edge, we estimate the thickness limit to around 40 MXene layers.

In contrast, the surface-sensitive TEY mode is not limited by the sample thickness and allows X-ray microscopic examination of samples too thick for conventional transmission detection. At the Ti L-edge, the information depth is around 2-4 nm, therefore mostly probing the first 1-2 MXene layers, regardless of the flake thickness. More details are on the information and probing depths of both transmission and TEY are available in the Supporting Information (SI).

2.2 Hyperspectral x-ray imaging

Multimodal SXM enables hyperspectral imaging where XAS is acquired simultaneously in transmission and TEY detection mode for each N-dimensional pixel, where N is the number

of different energy values. A workflow for the analysis of spectromicroscopic data collected for multilayered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene is presented in **Figure 2**. The process begins with the acquisition of images in both transmission and TEY modes at the Ti L-edge (step 1) with a typical pixel size of 50 nm.

Figure 2. **a** Workflow for spectromicroscopic data, collected for multilayered MS- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. Images in transmission and TEY mode, acquired at Ti L-edge (step 1) are preprocessed for drift correction and normalization (step 2). Then, images are reduced to a few components by performing a dimensionality reduction (step 3). Clustering is performed to these components to create the clustered transmission and TEY image (step 4). Clustered spectrum is extracted by averaging the preprocessed spectra, corresponding to pixels of a clustered area. Clustered spectra are shown in **b** for transmission and **c** for TEY mode. Cluster 1-3 and clusters I-III are produced after clustering separately the preprocessed transmission and TEY data, respectively. Scalebar: 2 μm .

Image registration with cross correlation is performed to the stack of transmission and TEY images to correct the drift during scanning. Transmission data are converted to optical density

(OD) and TEY data are divided by I_0 (step 2). Subsequently, dimensionality reduction techniques, such as Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are applied to the images, reducing them to a few essential components (step 3). Clustering, such as Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) and k-means, is performed on these components to create the clustered OD and TEY images (step 4). The suitable number of components and clusters is estimated by elbow and silhouette method (Figure S3), together the criteria for selection of dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques. From these clustered images, the corresponding X-ray absorption (XA) spectra are extracted by averaging the preprocessed spectra for pixels within a given clustered area. The clustered XA spectra are represented in both transmission (**Figure 2 b**) and TEY modes (**Figure 2 c**). The clustered spectra in transmission mode correspond mainly to areas with different thickness, whereas the ones in TEY, by areas with different electron emission behavior.

The main challenge is clustering the pixels that present similar chemical information independently from the MXene thickness or electron emission properties. In **Figure 2 c**, cluster 1 and 2 correspond to thicker areas with transmission spectra presenting absorption saturation distortions. Cluster 3 corresponds to the thinner part of MXene sample, yielding a transmission XAS Ti L-edge spectrum with distinct peaks that will be discussed in the following. Cluster I, II and III obtained from the TEY mode correspond to MXene areas with decreasing electron emission. Cluster I correspond to areas with increased TEY signal, caused by edge enhancement, given that these areas are usually the edges of the MXene particles. On the other hand, decreased signal of Cluster III can be explained by charging of the sample.

3. Results

3.1. Multimodal SXM imaging of individual $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes

Figure 3. **a** Transmission image, averaged at Ti L-edge, highlighting regions corresponding to a monolayer (dotted violet), 4-layered (dotted blue) and 5-layered HF- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes, with corresponding transmission spectra extracted from the orange dashed area (**b**). A non-conductive monolayer MXene flake (dotted red) is also indicated. **c** TEY image at 450 eV depicting the same regions as in **a**, with corresponding TEY spectra (**d**). Scalebar: 2 μm .

Representative SXM images of few-layered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes at the Ti L-edge are shown in **Figure 3**. Overlapping single and few-layered flakes on top of each other are visible in transmission and TEY mode. The comparison of transmission and TEY images reveals critical insights. The variation in OD in transmission images provide a detailed view of the thickness of MXene flakes, down to a monolayer (**Figure 3a**). The transmission XAS spectra at the Ti L-edge have similar spectral signature throughout the flake (**Figure 3b**). XAS at Ti L-edge is induced by excitation of Ti 2p electron to the unfilled 3d orbitals. Ti L_3 and L_2 edges arise from Ti $2p_{3/2}$ to Ti 3d and Ti $2p_{1/2}$ to Ti 3d transitions, respectively. sXAS can be employed for analysis of average t_{2g} – e_g crystal field splitting and relative t_{2g} to e_g bands

occupancy as discussed in the following section. In **Figure 3 a-b**, the main differences in spectra between the MXene areas are related to the thickness.

OD_{mono} is defined as the maximum L_3 peak intensity for a monolayer flake and estimated to be 0.039 ± 0.005 (Figure S5). Given the maximum OD of a MXene area, we can predict the number of layers of a flake, by exploiting the linear relation of OD with thickness.

Specifically, a 4-layered flake (blue dotted), with several flakes laying on top, is identified on **Figure 3a**, based on its respective maximum OD in the transmission spectra (**Figure 3 b**). It is partially covered by other flakes, except for the dashed orange areas corresponding to 5 layers, whose XA spectrum is provided. Therefore, we can state that a monolayer (dotted orange) lays on top of a 4-layered flake (dotted orange).

The surface sensitivity of TEY leads to a relatively uniform imaging of the MXene sample (**Figure 3 c**). The blue-colored spectrum is identical with the orange-colored one (**Figure 3 d**). Some other areas have also similar TEY XA spectra but shifted to higher or lower TEY. This difference is irrelevant with the thickness, and is rather related to various TEY phenomena, as discussed in SI (Figures S6-S8).

TEY images are utilized to identify areas with different conductivity, such as a non-conductive flake shown in dotted red (**Figure 3c**). **Figure 3 a-b** present indications that the non-conductive flake is monolayered, based on the transmission signal. This flake presents a constant offset in OD compared to the violet-dotted flake. This may be attributed to the existence of a thin film of chemical species below or above the non-conductive flake that are not titanium. The violet-dotted flake presents higher TEY signal than the red-dotted flake (**Figure 3d**), most probably because of a better electrical contact with the substrate and the other MXene flakes. The complete data set for few-layered MXene at Ti L-edge is presented in Figure S6 and equivalent measurements at O K-edge is included in Figure S7.

Normalization of the XA spectra for at least 20 layers leads to the same XA spectrum, allowing accurate layer estimation for the few-layered MXene. On the contrary, the normalized spectra for multilayered MXene do not lead to the same spectrum, because of the saturation due to increased thickness. Saturation effect does not hinder the acquisition of discrete peaks at Ti L-edge in the thinner areas (Cluster 3 of **Figure 2 b**) of multilayered MXene, but it does not allow an accurate estimation of maximum OD. This is best shown for the Cluster 1 in **Figure 2c**, corresponding to the areas with the highest thickness as shown by the fully saturated spectrum, whose maximum OD is decreased rather than increased with thickness compared to the Clusters 2 and 3.

3.2. Surface chemistry of HF- and MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene

The pristine multilayered MS- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene sample (**Figure 4 a and c**) exhibits significant similarities in XA spectra at the Ti L-edge compared to the pristine delaminated HF- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene sample (**Figure 3**). The splitting of the Ti L_2 and L_3 components are apparent for the MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene in both transmission (**Figure 4 b**) and TEY (**Figure 4 d**) modes. On the other hand, the L_2 e_g peak for the HF-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene is not pronounced. A noteworthy difference is presented by the L_3 e_g peak, which is shifted +0.4 eV for the MS-etched MXene compared to its counterpart in the HF-etched sample, indicated with a dashed red line.

Figure 4. Comparative analysis of normalized transmission and TEY XA spectra for HF- and MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene at the Ti L-edge (**a** and **c**) and O K-edge (**b** and **d**). To mitigate the impact of absorption saturation distortion, the spectra displayed for the MS-etched

Ti₃C₂T_x MXene have been selectively extracted from regions of reduced thickness. Both transmission and TEY spectra are normalized.

The broadening of the e_g peaks in comparison to the t_{2g} peaks, observed for both MXenes, can be explained by the a more extensive hybridization with the surface termination. The rationale behind this is that the e_g orbitals are directed towards the ligands, unlike the t_{2g} orbitals, which are oriented between the ligands^[34]. The L₂ edge shows more pronounced broad features, a consequence of the reduced lifetime of the 2p_{1/2} core holes and the near Coster-Krönig decay process^[35]. This may explain why e_g feature is discernible at Ti L₃-edge, and not at Ti L₂-edge for HF-etched MXene.

The increased e_g peak at the Ti L-edge for the MS-etched multilayered Ti₃C₂T_x MXene correlates with higher Ti oxidation state and increased oxygen termination of the MXene surface. The HF-etched MXene, in comparison, is primarily terminated by hydroxyl and fluorine. These surface termination groups possess a different symmetry than the bridging oxygen groups, thus contributing to a reduced e_g component. The broadened t_{2g} peak, observed in HF-etched Ti₃C₂T_x MXene, has previously been reported for titanium carbides and oxides with distorted octahedral symmetries due to intercalation^[36]. Surface termination groups, such as F and OH, may cause distortion of the Ti-O bonds.

The XAS at the O K-edge (**Figure 4 b** and **d**) corresponds to transitions from O 1s core levels to O 2p levels, hybridized with Ti 3d states. The peaks at the O K-edge, labeled as t_{2g} and e_g , are the transitions from O 1s to the hybridized orbital of O 2p with Ti 3d t_{2g} and e_g , respectively. They are located at 531.2 (531.4) and 533.6 (534.2) eV with an e_g to t_{2g} peak intensity ratio of 0.98 (0.92) for the MS-etched (HF-etched) Ti₃C₂T_x MXene in transmission mode (**Figure 4 b**). The e_g peak is detected at 0.6 eV higher energy for the HF-etched MXene. **Figure 4 d** presents the TEY spectrum at the O K-edge for both MS- and HF-etched MXenes, with the peaks at the same energy position for the MS-etched MXene in both detection modes. The quantitative interpretation of the TEY measurements, especially at O K-edge, is complex due to the charging phenomenon and carbon deposition during the measurement process (Figure S7 and Figure S9).

3.3. Surface and Bulk Responses of *post mortem* cycled MXene Anode in Li-ion Batteries

The *post-mortem* SXM analysis of MS-etched Ti₃C₂T_x MXene electrodes after cycling in a classical Li-ion battery (2 cycles from 3 V to 0 V) was attempted to identify the change of MXene chemical bonding after a few cycles. The SXM images averaged over the O K-edge

are shown in **Figure 5**. Battery components shown in **Figure 5 b**, such as green-colored cycled MXene electrodes, yellow-colored separator and red-colored carbonate species, are imaged with their corresponding transmission XA spectra **Figure 5 c**. Simultaneously, TEY image for the same area is also averaged over the energy range of O K-edge (**Figure 5 g**). Red-colored areas cover almost fully the MXene, leading to weak detection of MXene in TEY mode (**Figure 5 c and g**).

Figure 5. SXM data for cycled MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. **a** Transmission image at the O K-edge, along with **b** the clustered image and **c** corresponding transmission XAS spectra. **e** TEY image at the O K-edge, along with **f** the clustered image and **g** corresponding TEY spectra. Areas of MXene (green), separator (yellow), and electrolyte residues (red) are shown. **d-h** Comparative analysis at the Ti L-edge in **d** both transmission and **h** TEY modes for pristine and cycled MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. The spectra at O K- and Ti L-edge of pristine MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene (blue) are added for comparison. Scalebar: 2 μm .

The XA spectra at the O K-edge exhibit 6 components, labelled A_{1-6} which are visible in both detection modes (**Figure 5 c and g**), allowing the chemical identification of the various components of the dismantled cell. A_1 peak, located at 531.4 eV, is attributed to the t_{2g} peak of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. In TEY XA spectra (**Figure 5 g**), the A_1 peak is discernible in areas where the surface of MXene is not fully covered with electrolyte residues or other battery components. A_2 peak, located at 534.2 eV, could be attributed to the e_g peak of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene but it is shifted by +0.6 eV compared to pristine $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene.

The peaks A_2 (534.2 eV), A_3 (536.6 eV), A_4 (539.8 eV), A_5 (542.8 eV) and A_6 (545.4 eV) are related to transition to different CO bonds coming from the solid electrolyte interface

(SEI)^[37], electrolyte residues and other carbonate species^[36]. These species can be predominantly found in the red-colored regions. The most commonly detectable components of electrolyte residues are EC/DMC, and of SEI components are Li₂CO₃ and ROCOOLi. The A₂-A₆ components in the transmission XA spectrum and the overall spectrum in TEY mode can mainly be described by Li₂CO₃. Li₂CO₃ is the main component of SEI layer as a result of interaction between lithiated titanium carbide or oxide with the electrolyte. The SEI compounds may have reacted with air due to the short air exposure during the transfer to the X-ray microscope. Moreover, electrolyte has interacted with the surface and bulk of MXene. Therefore, the peaks of the carbonate species are broader than the ones presented in Figure S12 obtained from a region not in contact with the MXene. The clustering dataset at the O K-edge is presented in Figure S10.

Finally, transmission spectra at the Ti L-edge for the thin MXene areas, and the respective transmission and TEY XA spectra are obtained for pristine (blue) and cycled (green) multilayered Ti₃C₂T_x MXene (**Figure 5 d and h**, respectively). The L₃(L₂) *t*_{2g} and *e*_g peak for cycled MXene are located at 458.4 eV (463.6 eV) and 460.4 eV (465.8 eV), respectively for both transmission and TEY mode. The sensitivity of the *e*_g peak to the environment of MXene is remarkable. The *e*_g-to-*t*_{2g} peak intensity ratio is higher in TEY mode than in transmission mode, which can be interpreted by the surface being more oxidized than the bulk (increased Ti⁴⁺/Ti³⁺ ratio), probably due to exposure of the MXene surface to the electrolyte or to air.

Differences of XA spectra at Ti L-edge for pristine (blue) and cycled (green) Ti₃C₂T_x MXene in both transmission and TEY mode are observed. All peaks are shifted to higher photon energy for cycled compared to pristine Ti₃C₂T_xMXene. Additionally, the *e*_g peak of cycled MXene is 0.4 eV higher than the one of pristine Ti₃C₂T_x MXene. Ti *d* orbitals interact with species from their surroundings, which may create differences in the L₃-*e*_g peak, such as differences in energy between *d*_{x²-y² and *d*_{z²} orbitals, creating the splitting of L₃-*e*_g peak. Intercalation can cause increased *e*_g peak towards higher energy. It also explains the distorted symmetry of cycled MXene with an increase of the peak related to *d*_{z²} orbital. XA spectra at Ti L-edge do not indicate differences between pristine and cycled MXene, which are solely related to differences in the bulk and the surface.}

The A₃-A₆ peaks at O K-edge for the cycled MXene in transmission (**Figure 5 c**) are broader than the peaks of the average TEY spectrum (Figure S11). This may indicate some interaction of MXene interlayer with carbonate species and electrolyte. However, **Figure 5 g** shows that the surface of the MXene also interacts with various species in the battery, indicated by the

broader bands. The e_g peak at Ti L- and O K-edge for cycled MXene is located to higher photon energies than the one for pristine MXene. Increased e_g peak at Ti L-edge has previously been reported to be associated with cation intercalation during electrochemical cycling in a Li-ion battery^[38]. Increased e_g peak at O K-edge can be related to change of the bonding between Ti species with oxygen ones during reduction and oxidation reactions during electrochemical cycling. However, there may also be an overlap between A_2 peak assigned to CO_3^{2-} and the e_g peak of MXene at O K-edge without necessarily an interaction of the MXene with the carbonate species or the electrolyte.

The understanding of distortion of MXene's symmetry during cation intercalation and the subsequent changes in the XA spectrum can probably be further interpreted by DFT calculations. Moreover, during *post mortem* measurements the examined sample is exposed to air, which can possibly change the Ti chemical environment and the bonding with oxygen species. Further developments are ongoing to enable sample transfer without air exposure and for *in situ* electrochemical SXM measurements directly in liquid environment.

4. Conclusion

$\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes flakes, ranging from mono- to multilayers, were imaged using multimodal SXM with a spatial resolution of less than 50 nm. Simultaneous hyperspectral X-ray imaging in transmission and TEY modes provide insights into the local chemistry of the MXene surface and bulk regions on individual flakes. SXM allows the monitoring of MXene flake thickness and electron emission properties at the sub-flake level. Local XAS measurements have a high chemical sensitivity to the Ti and O bonding configurations, hence to the surface chemistry of MXene. The Ti chemical bonding differs dramatically between HF-etched and MS-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes explained by the larger content of O-termination in MS- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. *Post mortem* analysis of a MXene-based Li-ion battery, allows identification of both pristine and electrochemically cycled $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. Upon comparing pristine and cycled MXene, we discern signs of a chemical interaction between Li and the MXene flakes. Furthermore, surface-sensitive TEY measurements hint at potential surface reactions between the MXene and the electrolyte during the electrochemical cycling process. This distinction underscores the complex interplay of bulk intercalation and surface phenomena in these 2D materials.

5. Experimental Section/Methods

SXM imaging

The measurements were performed at the ultra-high vacuum scanning X-ray microscopy (UHV-SXM) 'MAXYMUS' microscope endstation at the UE46-PGM2 undulator beamline at HZB/BESSY II. Surface-sensitive total electron yield (TEY) measurements were conducted simultaneously with standard transmission measurements by amplifying the sample current using a commercial amplifier from FEMTO Messtechnik GmbH, then converting it to corresponding frequency values. To boost the total sample current, we set the OSA - a device that prevents zero-order light from hitting the sample - to a positive bias voltage of approximately + 30 V. This approach reduced the number of unwanted electrons released from the Fresnel ZP due to incoming X-ray excitation. The transmission X-ray flux was recorded using an avalanche photodiode.

Sample preparation

SiN membranes (Silson) with high crystallinity for both transmission and TEY experiments were used for this study. The membrane size was 1 mm x 1mm with a thickness of 100 nm, and the Si frame size was 5 mm x 5mm with a thickness of 200 μm .

MXene synthesis

Two types of MXenes were used for this study: few-layered HF-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes and multilayered molten salt (MS)-etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes. MS-etched MXene was prepared via molten salt shielded synthesis method as previously reported^[39]. Specifically, 1 g of Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase powder was combined with a eutectic salt (NaCl:KCl in a 1:1 molar ratio) in a weight ratio between 1:6. This blend was ground for ten minutes using a mortar and pestle. The ground powder was then subjected to uniaxial pressure in a 20 mm diameter steel die under a load of 50 kg cm^{-2} to form a pellet. This formed pellet was then placed in a cylindrical alumina crucible. Next, a mixture of salts (8.7 g of NaCl, 11.2 g of KCl, and 4 g of CuCl_2) was added to a 30 mL crucible to cover the pellet following ten minutes of milling. This crucible was then sealed with an alumina lid and positioned in a muffle furnace. The furnace was heated to 700°C at a rate of 10°C per minute and maintained at this temperature for 40 minutes. After the furnace cooled to room temperature, the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{Cu}$ mixture was repeatedly rinsed with deionized water to rid it of salts. The Cu from the resultant $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{Cu}$ mixture was then eliminated by washing it with 100 mL of 0.5 MAPS solution for one hour at room temperature. This solution was then washed more than five times with deionized water

and filtered. Finally, the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene powder was left to dry under vacuum at room temperature for 12 hours.

Electrochemical cycling

Two-electrodes Swagelok cell was used for the electrochemical measurement, with the working electrode composed of MS- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene powder mixed with carbon black with a weight ratio of 9:1. Metallic lithium foil is used as counter electrode, reference electrode and LP30 (1M LiPF_6 in 1:1 vol/vol ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate) as the electrolyte, and Whatman glassy fiber GF/A was used as separator. Cyclic voltammetry tests were conducted in potential range of 0.2-3 V vs. Li^+/Li , with a scan rate of 0.5 mV/s. Upon reduction during the first cycle, the formation of a solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer is expected.

Post-cycling, the MXene powder was recovered from the cell and rinsed with dimethyl carbonate (DC) to remove excess electrolyte. Following sample loading into the SXM hatch, the DC was evaporated due to the high vacuum conditions.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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T.P. conceptualized and supervised the project. P.B. performed all the SXM experiment with help from F.A. and M.W.. F.A. performed the data analysis under the supervision of T.P.. H.S. synthesized the multilayered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene and performed electrochemical cycling. P.B. synthesized the few-layered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, with the MAX precursor that J.G.J provided. F.A. and T.P. wrote the manuscript with contributions from the authors.

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